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Post-harvest Technology in Cassava Processing as Correlate to Food Security in Kwali Area Council of FCT Abuja, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the effects of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food security in the Kwali Area Council of FCT Abuja, Nigeria. Four research questions were answered and four hypotheses tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The population for this study was 30,500 farmers. The sample size for this study was 275 registered cassava processors in the Kwali Area Council. The instrument for the study was a structured questionnaire titled 'Post-harvest Technology in Cassava Processing as Correlate for Food Security Questionnaire (PTCPAFSQ). Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the research hypotheses. The result of the findings revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food availability ($r = 0.370$). The findings also revealed a perfect positive correlation ($r = 0.644$). The findings of the study revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food utilization. ($r = 0.965$). Finally, the finding revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technology in cassava production for food stability ($r = 0.370$). The study concluded that post-harvest technologies have a significant effect on the availability, accessibility, utilization, and stability of cassava products. It was recommended that the authority of the agricultural development project (ADP) should facilitate the provision of post-harvest equipment to farmers in order to enhance cassava availability. Cassava farmers, through their registered cooperative societies, should make an effort to establish post-harvest centres where cassava is processed to assure the stability of cassava products.

Keywords: Post-harvest, Technology, Processing, Correlate and Food Security

INTRODUCTION

Application of innovation in agricultural production offers numerous advantages to farmers. Advancements in agricultural production also lead to its efficient utilization, better management, and overall resilience, especially in the production of cassava. Cassava (*Manihot-esculenta*) is a dicotyledonous plant that belongs to the family Euphorbiaceae (Latif & Müller, 2015). It is a woody shrub used as a staple food in the world. Cassava can be eaten fresh, roasted, fried, or boiled. Cassava is a perennial plant, and it is mostly cultivated in tropical and sub-tropical regions as an annual crop for its edible starchy tuberous root (McGregor, Manley, Tubuna, Deo & Bourke, 2020). There are different varieties of cassava; these include TME 419, Dixon, formerly known as 0581 (TMS-9800581), Farmer's Pride, formerly known as 1632 (TMS-981632), Fine Face, formerly known as 0505 (TMS-980505) and Sunshine, formerly known as 0593 (TMS-070593) (Sike-Ezo, 2024). Cassava is processed to extract cassava starch, called garri, which is used for food, animal feed, and industrial purposes. According to the Agricultural Research Development Council (2024), cassava is also used as an animal feed and in the manufacture of different industrial products. Garri is an edible coarse flour obtained by grating cassava roots, pressing moisture off the obtained grated pulp, and finally drying.

According to IITA in Echebiri and Edaba (2018), about 1.2 million hectares of land are needed for the production of cassava to meet demand for some of the cassava by-products and derivatives, such as ethanol, cassava-based constituents in sugar syrup, high-quality cassava flour, garri, and cassava-based adhesives such as cassava starch, caustic soda, formaldehyde, hydrochloric acid and sodium silicate. Phillips, Taylor, Sanni and Akoroda (2019) said that the total output of about 59.5 million metric tons of cassava produced in Nigeria has the economic potential to generate revenues. The local value-addition to cassava via local manufacturing and processing could potentially unlock about \$16 million in taxes to the government (Echebiri & Edaba, 2018). Adeniji, Ega, Akoroda, Adeniyi and Ugwu (2023) opined that cassava is important, not just as a food crop but also as a major source of income generation for its producers. Cassava generates cash income for the largest number of households, contributing positively to poverty alleviation among farmers. Value addition is ensured in cassava production by post-harvest technologies.

Post-harvest technology refers to a procedure and action used to maintain the marketability, safety, and quality of agricultural products following harvest (Santosh and Ali, 2024). This stage of agricultural production is crucial since it has a direct impact on the harvested crops' shelf life, nutritional value, and overall worth. According to Barrett et al., in Santosh and Ali (2024), post-harvest handling involves a series of activities, including harvesting, sorting, cleaning, packing, storage, and transportation, all of which play a crucial role in maintaining the freshness and quality of agricultural commodities. Technologies used for cassava processing include vibrating sieves, abrasive peelers, motorized graters, drum dryers, and screw jacks (Mgbakor, 2015). Cassava processing techniques include peeling, pressing, grating, and washing. The application of technology to augment traditional cassava processing assures safety and well-detoxified products. In cassava production, technology plays a crucial role in the processing activities. Post-harvest technology enhances the safety of cassava, prevents the loss of huge amounts of money invested in production and facilitates the transformation of raw cassava into a finished, polished final product.

According to Onyenwoke and Simonyan (2014), cassava undergoes post-harvest physiological deterioration (PPD) once the tubers are separated from the main plant, which is one of the main obstacles currently preventing farmers from exporting fresh cassava abroad, thereby generating income from foreign exchange. Processing is a very good vehicle for addressing some health-related problems in cassava and also serves as security of food. Asige and Omuse (2022) found a strong, positive, and significant correlation between post-harvest technology and food security. Adejumo, Okoruwaa, Abass and Salmana (2020) noted that investment in improved post-harvest technologies by cassava starch processors and other stakeholders would increase income, thus improving the welfare of producers. According to Daemo, Yohannes, Beyene and Abteu (2023), the application of post-harvest technology in cassava production positively affects the utilization proportion of 51.87% of the farmers who utilized

cassava for home consumption, 43.68% for the market, and 4.26% for animal feed. The consumption pattern indicated that 46.50% was boiled roots, 15.00% was cooked flour, and 38.50% was boiled roots and cooked flour. This indicates that the farmers' consumption patterns and processing methods are very traditional. Uchechukwu-Agua and Caleb (2015) found that post-harvest handling, processing, and storage of fresh cassava root play a significant role in storage and minimal processing on sustainable cassava production. Post-harvest technologies in crop production are proper harvesting, handling, storage techniques and processing.

Cassava processing is the conversion of the fresh root into other forms acceptable to consumers. There are numerous ways of processing and consuming cassava depending on locality. Processing of cassava involves various stages such as fermentation, drying, and cooking (Oyewole, 2024). Fermentation is an important method commonly used in cassava processing. The fermentation techniques for cassava are categorized into solid-state fermentation and submerged fermentation. Oyewole (2024) added that solid-state fermentation, typified by *gari* production, involves the use of grated or sliced cassava pieces that are allowed to undergo fermentation while exposed to the natural atmosphere or pressed in a hygienic bag. The process of submerged fermentation involves the soaking of whole peeled cassava, which is cut, unpeeled roots in water for several periods as typified by the production of molded pieces typically called *fufu* in Nigeria. In a traditional setting, the cassava is fermented for a period of 4 to 6 days in order to enhance the effect of sufficient detoxification of the cassava roots. Application of technology for cassava processing assures food security.

Food security means having, at all times, both physical and economic access to sufficient food to meet dietary needs for a productive and healthy life (United Nations Agency for International Development, 2024). A family is food secure when its members do not live in hunger or fear of hunger. Food security is the state of having reliable access to a sufficient quantity of affordable, nutritious food. A country that ensures food is available to all its citizens is a strong and stable one. Food security is an economic and social condition of ready access by all members of a household to nutritionally adequate and safe food. Essentially, Bajagai (2013) posited that food security can be described as a phenomenon relating to individuals.

It is the nutritional status of the individual household member that is the ultimate focus and the risk of that adequate status not being achieved or becoming undermined. Food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food which meets their dietary requires and food preferences for an active and healthy life. Food security is the outcome of food system operating efficiently. There are several dimensions: availability; access; utilization; and stability (Manikas, Ali & Sundarami, 2023).

Technology advancements not only help to feed local communities, but also create new commercial markets. With these new markets comes more money for families to escape poverty (FAO, 2014). However, observation has shown that cassava farmers in Northern Cross River state record post-harvest losses due to processing facilities (Oluwatusin, 2017). The large quantity of cassava produced in Kwali Area Council is perishes. Farmers always account for great loss of cassava after harvest. According to Nigeria Agricultural Promotion Policy in Oluwatusin (2017), the post-harvest loss rate of cassava is put at 60 percent. Due to loss of cassava during harvest as a result of lack of processing factories, the cassava is sold at ridiculous low prices to middlemen by farmers. It against this background that the study is designed to exploit post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food security in Kwali Area Council of FCT, Abuja

Objectives

1. To determine the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food availability;
2. To ascertain the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food accessibility;
3. To find out the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food utilization;
4. To examine the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food stability;

Research Questions

1. What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food availability?

2. What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food accessibility?
3. What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava production for food utilization?
4. What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food stability?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between post-harvest technology in cassava processing and food availability.
2. There is no significant relationship between post-harvest technology in cassava processing and food accessibility.
3. There is no significant relationship between post-harvest technology in cassava processing and food utilization.
4. There is no significant relationship between post-harvest technology in cassava processing and food stability.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Kwali Area Council of the FCT Abuja. The study adopted a survey research design. The population for this study was 30,500 farmers. The sample size for this study was 275 registered cassava processors in Kwali Area Council. The instrument for the study was a structured questionnaire titled ‘Effects of Post-Harvest Technology in Cassava Production for Food Security Questionnaire (EPTCPFSQ)’. The instrument was validated by two experts, one in the Department of Crop Protection and the other from the Science and Environmental Education Department, all in the University of Abuja. In order to ensure the reliability of the instrument, it was subjected to a trial testing using twenty (20) cassava processors in the Gwagwalada Area Council of FCT, Abuja. The data obtained from the trial testing was analyzed using Cronbach's alpha. A coefficient of 0.87 was obtained, which was adjudged reliable for the items. Descriptive statistics, precisely mean and standard deviation, were used to answer the research questions, while the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This data collected was analysed, presented in Tables and interpreted below.

Research Question 1: *What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food availability?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Cassava Processors on the Effect of Post-Harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Availability (N = 275)

S/N	Items Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Improve post-harvest methods reduce losses	3.34	0.92	Agree
2	Enhance quality, and extend shelf life	3.36	0.91	Agree
3	Increases food availability and income for producers	3.18	0.78	Agree
4	Increases the amount of cassava available for consumption	1.51	0.88	Disagree
5	Increase the time cassava roots can be stored before spoilage.	2.51	1.00	Agree
6	Enhances increase of farmers’ income thereby making the cassava more accessible to consumers	2.72	1.16	Agree
Grand Mean		2.77	0.94	

Result in Table 1 show that out of 6 items, 5 had their mean values range from 2.72 to 3.36 with a grand mean value of 2.77. These values were above the benchmark of 2.50. This means that post-harvest technology in cassava processing has an effect on food availability.

Research Question 2: *What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava production for food accessibility?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Cassava Processors on the Effect of Post-Harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Accessibility (N = 275)

S/N	Items Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Minimize losses during handling, storage, and processing, ensuring more of the cassava crop reaches consumers	3.40	0.84	Agree
2	Transforms cassava products into more stable and readily usable forms	3.22	0.95	Agree
3	Helps to remove cyanogenic compounds (toxins) in cassava, improving food safety	3.35	0.78	Agree
4	Ensures that cassava is available to a wider range of consumers	3.06	0.97	Agree
Grand Mean		3.26	0.88	

Result in Table 2 show that all 4 items had their mean values range from 3.06 to 3.40 with a grand mean value of 3.26. These values were above the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that post-harvest technology in cassava processing has an effect on food accessibility.

Research Question Three: *What is the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava production for food utilization?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Cassava Processors on the Effect of Post-Harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Utilization (N = 275)

S/N	Items Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Helps to preserve fresh cassava, extending its shelf life and reducing losses	3.02	0.93	Agree
2	Creates more marketable and diverse products	3.24	0.98	Agree
3	Allows for a wider range of uses, from food and beverages to industrial applications	3.07	0.92	Agree
4	Contributes to food security by reducing waste and making cassava more available throughout the year.	3.16	0.98	Agree
5	Increases income generation farmers and processors	3.19	0.94	Agree
6	Helps to maintain the nutritional value of cassava.	3.24	0.89	Agree
7	Assures deliverance of products are used in various industries	3.57	0.84	Agree
Grand Mean		3.21	0.93	

Result in Table 3 show that all 7 items had their mean values range from 3.02 to 3.57, with a grand mean value of 3.21. These values were above the benchmark of 2.50. This is an indication that post-harvest technology in cassava processing has an effect on food utilization.

Research Question 4: *What is the effect of post-harvest technology of cassava processing for food stability?*

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of Cassava Processors on the Effect of Post-Harvest Technology in Cassava processing for Food Stability (N = 275)

S/N	Items Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1	Reduces post-harvest physiological deterioration (PPD) and extending storage life	3.31	1.09	Agree
2	Increases income generation farmers and processors	2.99	1.03	Agree
3	Helps to maintain the nutritional value of cassava.	2.97	1.04	Agree
4	Assures deliverance of products are used in various industries	3.26	1.04	Agree
Grand Mean		3.13	1.05	

Result in Table 4 show that all 4 items had their mean values range from 2.97 to 3.31 with a grand mean value of 3.13. The values were above the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that post-harvest technology in cassava processing has an effect on food stability.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female cassava processors on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food availability

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Result of Post-harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Availability

		Post-harvest Technology	Food Availability
Post-harvest Technology	Pearson Correlation	1	.370**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	275	275
Food Availability	Pearson Correlation	.370**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The result in Table 5 show *r* value of 0.370 at a 2-tailed level of significance. The result is statistically significant. This means that there is a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava processing for food availability.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female cassava processors on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food accessibility

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Result of Post-harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Accessibility

		Post-harvest Technology	Food Accessibility
Post-harvest Technology	Pearson Correlation	1	.644**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	275	275
Food Accessibility	Pearson Correlation	.644**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The result in Table 6 shows an *r* value of 0.644 at a 2-tailed level of significance. The result is statistically significant. This means that there is a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food accessibility.

Research Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female cassava processors on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food utilization

Table 7: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Result Post-harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Utilization

		Post-harvest Technology	Food Utilization
Post-harvest Technology	Pearson Correlation	1	.965**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	275	275
Food Utilization	Pearson Correlation	.965**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The result in Table 5 show r value of 0.965 at a 2-tailed level of significance. The result is statistically significant. This means that there is a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food utilization.

Research Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female cassava processors on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food stability

Table 8: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Result of Post-harvest Technology in Cassava Processing for Food Stability

		Post-harvest Technology	Food Stability
Post-harvest Technology	Pearson Correlation	1	.430**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	275	275
Food Stability	Pearson Correlation	.430**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	275	275

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The result in Table 5 show r value of 0.370 at a 2-tailed level of significance. The result is statistically significant. This means that there is a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food stability.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava processing for food availability revealed that post-harvest technology improves post-harvest methods and reduces losses; reduces losses, enhances quality, and extends shelf life; increases food availability and income for producers; increases the time cassava roots can be stored before spoilage; and enhances the increase of farmers’ income, thereby making the cassava more accessible to consumers. The test of hypothesis one revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava processing for food availability. The finding supports a report by Asige and Omuse (2022), which found a strong, positive, and significant correlation between post-harvest technology and food security. Also, the finding did not affirm that of Adejumo, Okoruwaa, Abass and Salmana (2020) who found out that investment in improved post-harvest technologies by cassava starch processors and other stakeholders would increase income, thus improving welfare.

Also, findings on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava production for food accessibility revealed that post-harvest technology minimizes losses during handling, storage, and processing, ensuring more of the cassava crop reaches consumers; transforms cassava products into more stable and readily usable forms; helps to remove cyanogenic compounds (toxins) in cassava, improving food safety; and ensures that cassava is available to a wider range of consumers. The test of hypothesis two revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food accessibility. The finding is not different from a report by Uchechkwu-Agua and Caleb (2015) who found that the role of post-harvest handling of freshly harvested cassava root is essential, owing to the rapid physiological deterioration of the root soon after harvest. Processing cassava root into other food forms such as fufu, garri, starch and high-quality flour enhances stability and long-term storage.

Similarly, findings on the effect of post-harvest technology in cassava production for food utilization revealed that post-harvest helps to preserve fresh cassava, extending its shelf life and reducing losses; creates more marketable and diverse products; allows for a wider range of uses, from food and beverages to industrial applications; increases income generation for farmers and processors; and assures deliverance of products that are used in various industries, among others. The test of hypothesis two revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food utilization. The finding agrees with Onyenwoke and Simonyan (2014) who found that processing cassava affects the nutritional value of cassava roots through modification and losses in nutrients of high value.

The processing methods include peeling, boiling, steaming, slicing, grating, soaking or steeping, fermenting, pounding, roasting, pressing, drying, and milling. The products from cassava are High Quality Cassava Flour (HQCF), cassava chips, garri, starch and ethanol.

Finally, the finding on the effect of post-harvest technology of cassava processing for food stability revealed that post-harvest technology reduces post-harvest physiological deterioration (PPD) and extends storage life, increases income generation for farmers and processors, helps to maintain the nutritional value of cassava, and assures deliverance of products are used in various industries. The test of hypothesis two revealed a perfect positive correlation between post-harvest technologies in cassava production for food stability. The finding corroborates a report by Uchechkwu-Agua and Caleb (2015) which found out that understanding the role of optimum post-harvest handling, processing, and storage techniques would alleviate some concerns of food insecurity.

CONCLUSION

Cassava processing has been found to be an important activity in agriculture. Post-harvest operations add value to cassava products. The study has established that processing adds value to cassava products. The study concludes that post-harvest technologies have a significant effect on the availability, accessibility, utilization, and stability of cassava products.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The authority of the agricultural development project (ADP) should facilitate the provision of post-harvest equipment to farmers in order to enhance cassava availability.
2. Extension agents should ensure that cassava farmers are given adequate training on processing activities to enhance cassava accessibility.
3. Extension agents should encourage farmers to adopt the use of post-harvest technologies to ensure good cassava utilization.
4. Cassava farmers, through their registered cooperative societies, should make an effort to establish post-harvest centres where cassava is processed to assure stability of cassava products.

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